

Real Object Manipulation in the Physical Metaverse via Avatarm

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Abstract—Metaverse is an immersive shared space that remote users can access through virtual and augmented reality interfaces, enabling their avatars to interact with each other and the surrounding. Although digital objects can be manipulated, physical objects cannot be touched, grasped, or moved within the metaverse due to the lack of a suitable interface. This work proposes a solution to overcome this limitation by introducing the “Physical Metaverse”, a shared environment populated by “Avatars”: an avatar enhanced with a robotic arm that performs physical manipulative tasks while remaining entirely hidden from user’s view through diminished reality techniques.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Interaction, Augmented Reality, Teleoperation

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-robot collaboration has become very popular with the advent of domestic and assistive robotics, and it is interesting to note that digital environments gives the possibility to realize interfaces with the aim of helping people. Among various ways to utilize auxiliary robotics for wellness of persons, the metaverse offers captivating opportunities. The virtual spaces of the metaverse consist of computer-designed environments and digital twins of real objects and are populated by avatars, the graphical counterparts of the users. To increase the sense of immersion in the virtual experience, researchers are tackling the challenge of integrating the haptic channel with the audio and video streams [1]–[3]. However, the key feature that is currently missing is the physical interaction with real remote objects. To overcome this limitation, this work presents the concept of a Physical Metaverse which will be enabled by a new interface enhancing the virtual avatar with manipulation capabilities that we will call the Avatarm.

II. AVATARM AND PHYSICAL METAVERSE

The Avatarm consists of an avatar augmented by a robotic arm that performs physical manipulation tasks while remaining entirely hidden in the metaverse. In this way, the users have the illusion that the avatar is directly manipulating objects without the mediation of a robot (Fig. 1). The scenario represented in Fig. 2 will be instrumental in explaining the framework of the Physical Metaverse. Let us consider two people, Alice (A) and Blair (B), which are physically remote and can interact in the metaverse, sharing an augmented version of A’s physical environment. Alice observes her workspace through a head-mounted display (HMD), while Blair observes the same environment from a remote camera that streams into his own HMD. B is the Avatarm of the scenario, hence she can

Fig. 1: Avatarm representative scenario. On the left the scene captured by the real camera, on the right the scene as seen by the Avatarm user.

manipulate real objects in A’s physical environment exploiting the robot placed on A’s desk. In the virtual world, the robot is removed from the video stream and substituted with B’s virtual arm thanks to the an overlap of panels.

In what follows, we will describe the two main parts of the Avatarm working framework: *i*) the robot canceling method, and *ii*) the robot motion control. Finally, we will report a demonstrative scenario of the Physical Metaverse.

A. Robot Cancelling Method

Differently from the existing vision-based solutions, we propose a technique to determine the region to be removed by using the robot’s CAD model which moves according to its kinematics. In the proposed framework, the real-time cancellation of the robotic arm is performed through an ad-hoc virtual environment.

A digital camera placed in the virtual environment records the CAD model while it is moving in front of a black panel. A region-based segmentation and binarization algorithm takes as input the frames from the virtual camera and estimates the pixels containing portions of robot. The output is a binary mask $M(t)$, in which elements $m_{x,y}(t)$ are equal to 1 if the pixel in position (x, y) of the frame acquired at time t contains part of the robot, 0 otherwise. The image frames acquired by the real camera $I(t)$ are projected on a virtual panel. The latter is overlapped by a second virtual panel, which is used to stream frames that are a combination of the background image (acquired before placing the robot) $H(t)$ and binary mask $M(t)$. Thanks to the panels overlapping, the two images $I(t)$ and $\bar{H}(t)$ are fused together, generating the image $\bar{I}(t)$,

Fig. 2: Physical Metaverse framework. User (B) is the Avatarm of the scene and she can manipulate real objects in the remote environment of user (A) exploiting the robot which remains hidden from view inside the HMD.

whose pixels result:

$$\varphi_{\tilde{I}}(x, y, t) = \begin{cases} \varphi_I(x, y, t) & \forall x, y : m_{x,y}(t) = 0; \\ \varphi_H(x, y) & \forall x, y : m_{x,y}(t) = 1. \end{cases}$$

At this point, the robotic arm is made transparent in the resulting frames $\tilde{I}(t)$ by replacing the pixels within the mask with portions of the background image. The result is finally rendered into the user's HMD.

B. Robot Motion Control

To ensure the realism of the interaction, we sought to match movements and forces applied on the gravity centers of the real object and its digital twin. Thus, we implemented a mapping algorithm based on the contact effects on the two objects. When the virtual hand grasps the digital twin, from the virtual scene we can compute at each time instant both pose variation $\nu_v(t)$ of all contact points, as well as the generalized forces λ_v applied to the virtual object. Using the grasping theory and the kinetostatic duality, we compute the joint reference torques $\tau_r(t)$ and velocities $\dot{q}_r(t)$ as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tau_r(t) \\ \dot{q}_r(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N(G_r)\tilde{\Gamma}_r\Gamma_vN(G_v)^\dagger J^T \\ (G_r^T)^\dagger kG_v^T J^\dagger \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_v(t) \\ \nu_v(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

where G_i and $N(G_i)$ are the grasping matrices and the projectors onto the null space of the grasping matrices computed in virtual ($i = v$) and real ($i = r$) worlds. J is the Jacobian matrix of the robotic arm. With $(\cdot)^\dagger$ we denote the pseudo-inverse operator, while Γ is the average operator in form of matrix. k is a scale factor used to match the workspaces of robot and virtual hand.

III. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

To demonstrate the feasibility of the Physical Metaverse, we tested the system in a real applicative scenario in which the Avatarm was used to remotely pour a glass of water.

The experimental setup consisted of a desk with some objects of common use. A Sawyer (Rethink Robotics GmbH, DE) was used, while the cancellation layers were implemented with Unity Engine (Unity Technologies, US) using frames acquired by 1080p USB webcams. A Leap Motion Controller (UltraLeap inc., US) was used to track the hand. A website showing the system is publicly available at <http://physicalmetaverse.org>. The pouring task was repeated 10 times. The position and the

Fig. 3: The trajectories of the real bottle (solid line) and its digital twin (dotted line) during a trial of the pouring task.

orientation errors between the real bottle and its digital twin were computed. All users completed the task successfully. In Fig. 3 we report the paths obtained in a representative trial. The resulting position error, computed as the root mean square error of the norm among all the trials, is 0.0173 ± 0.0132 m. Similarly, we computed the average orientation error among all trials as the root mean square error of roll, pitch and yaw, obtaining 1.81 ± 1.80 deg, 2.08 ± 2.49 deg, 3.99 ± 5.27 deg.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We introduced the Avatars, a new generation of avatars with the ability to manipulate physical objects in the metaverse. Their implementation broadens the perspective of the digital interaction toward the Physical Metaverse, an extended world where users have real object mediated communication. Future work could explore how the Avatarm affects the feeling of collaboration between users engaged in interactive or assistive tasks.

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